

**Measurement and computational model of the
maximum stable gain in acoustic feedback scenarios**

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ABSTRACT

The behaviour of a sound reinforcement system, such as Public Address (PA) system, can be disturbed by the acoustic feedback phenomenon. In such a system, several microphones and loudspeakers are placed in the same room. When the amplified signal radiated by the loudspeakers goes into the microphones, the system could show instability. It then, when it can perceive the phenomenon known as the Larsen effect, or howling effect.

The potential of automatic feedback control is the reason why researchers have focused on it during the last years.

This research is based on experimental results from acoustics measurements.

So, this master thesis proposes a methodology to measure the maximum stable gain (maximum achievable amplification) in a given microphone-loudspeaker-room scenario just below feedback.

KEY WORDS

Acoustic feedback, maximum stable gain, Larsen effect, howling, automatic feedback control, acoustic measurements...

RESUMEN

El comportamiento de un sistema de refuerzo sonoro como un sistema de Public Address (PA), puede ser alterado por el fenómeno de la realimentación acústica. En un sistema como éste, varios micrófonos y altavoces se colocan en la misma sala. Cuando la señal amplificada se cuela por los micrófonos, el sistema podría mostrar inestabilidad. Es entonces cuando se puede percibir el fenómeno conocido como efecto Larsen, o "*howling effect*".

El potencial del control automático de la realimentación es la razón por la cual los investigadores se han centrado en él durante los últimos años.

Esta investigación está basada en resultados experimentales de medidas acústicas.

Por tanto, esta tesis fin de master propone una metodología para medir la máxima ganancia estable (máxima amplificación alcanzable) en un escenario dado, micrófono-altavoz-sala, justo antes de la realimentación.

PALABRAS CLAVE

Realimentación acústica, máxima ganancia estable, efecto Larsen, "*howling*", control automático de la realimentación, medidas acústicas...

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1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Motivation

The correct operation of sound reinforcement systems such a public address system (PA) can be disturbed by the acoustic feedback problem. In the same acoustic environment, loudspeakers and microphones are placed in the same room, so, the amplified signal that comes through the loudspeakers returns to the microphone in a closed loop (see fig. 1). This phenomenon deteriorates the sound quality and limits the achievable amplification. The most characteristic effect produced by this acoustic coupling, between loudspeakers and microphone, is the howling effect [1], also known, as the *Larsen effect*.

Fig 1: Acoustic feedback scenario

This howling effect has been researched in order to avoid it, or in any case, in reducing its impact in the performance of the sound reinforcement. *Acoustic*

feedback control is then, the process of reducing the acoustic feedback problem, completely or partially. This acoustic control can be performed in two different ways: manual (technicians needed) or automatic (methods implemented on a digital signal processor). In the last years, the researchers had focused in the last one because of its potential. In the other hand, this feedback effect has been also applied to many desired proposes, for example, as a feedback simulator for an electric guitar (fig. 2).

Fig 2: Softube's software (VST plugin) for acoustic feedback simulation

This master thesis proposes a methodology to measure this phenomenon, in order to built a computational model to achieve the maximum stable gain (see chapter 2.3 for details) of an acoustic feedback scenario, such as the one presented in the figure 1. This methodology fills a gap between old ones [2][3][4] (such as based in Vacuum Tube Voltmeter Measures) and current equipment and technology.

1.2. Goals

In order to achieve the main goal of the thesis, several milestones have been defined:

1. Set-up of a controlled scenario for acoustic feedback simulation.
2. Measurements and recordings of feedback simulation.
3. Analysis of the data collected in the second milestone.
4. Based on the analysis of the collected data, generation of an audio dataset.
5. Spectral descriptors analysis and machine learning.

2. STATE OF THE ART

2.1. The acoustic feedback problem

In a typical sound reinforcement with a PA system (fig. 3), several microphones are positioned to catch the sound sources. Then, microphone signals are mixed in a mixing console where can be processed. After this, the signal goes to an amplifier, which routes the signal to the loudspeakers, located in order to aim the audience. Microphones and loudspeakers are positioned taking into account their directivity. Usually, is made in this way to avoid direct coupling between the two devices. However, in an acoustic environment such a room, exist boundaries (walls, ceiling, floor), objects (furniture) and subjects (performers, audience), which reflect the sound. These reflections are guilty of an indirect acoustic coupling, responsible of acoustic feedback phenomenon.

Fig 3: Public address reinforcement system scenario

Two signals can be modelled in a single PA scenario (fig. 3): the electroacoustic forward path, or gain (G), and the acoustic feedback path (F). In a single-channel

sound reinforcement system (see fig. 4), the input signal (S) is captured by the microphone (M). Then, this signal is amplified by a broadband G factor. Finally, the signal radiated by the loudspeaker (L) comes back to the microphone through the room, by a gain factor F, which depends on the frequency.

Fig 4: Single-channel sound reinforcement system

The acoustic feedback is modelled as a system theory problem. Thus, the signal captured by the microphone (M) is:

$$L = G \cdot M = (S + L \cdot F) \cdot G = S \cdot G + L \cdot F \cdot G \quad (1)$$

And the overall transfer function can be calculated as:

$$H = \frac{L}{S} = \frac{G}{1 - F \cdot G} \quad (2)$$

Where G and F represent the discrete Fourier transform (DFT) of the forward and feedback path. The factor FG is also known as the “loop response”, been called its module, the “loop gain”, and its phase, the “loop phase” [1]. This kind of systems can become unstable, and the oscillations produced by the system, are perceived as howling, also known as the *Larsen Effect*. It is well known that the system exhibits

instability when two conditions are fulfilled, at least at one frequency: *Nyquist Stability Criterion* [5]. These conditions are:

1. The “loop gain” is equal or greater than 1:

$$|F \cdot G| \geq 1 \quad (3)$$

2. The “loop phase” at this frequency is an integer of 2π :

$$\angle F \cdot G = 2n\pi, \quad n \in \mathbb{Z} \quad (4)$$

Feedback gain (F) is between 0 and 1, since is a proportional amount of the original signal (L). So, due to dissipation in the air, absorbers, etcetera, is never going to be greater than 1. This value is fixed by the characteristics of the room and depends on the frequency. In the other hand, forward gain factor (G), is the gain applied to the source, so, always is going to be greater than the unity. If it is 1, there is no amplification that means that the system is turned off.

So, if the system is excited by a frequency for which these two conditions are satisfied, the closed-loop system will become unstable, and in consequence, the howling will be heard.

2.2. Maximum stable gain

According to *Nyquist Stability Criterion*, the maximum achievable amplification gain (before the system shows instability) is limited by the magnitude of the loop response, at which the phase is an integer of $2n\pi$. Phase of the loop response can change quickly over the frequency, so the magnitude is a good indicator for the applicable gain [6]. Thus, the *Maximum Stable Gain* (MSG) is defined as the maximum amplification that can be applied to a close-loop system before it becomes unstable. This measure for the system is also defined for a broadband gain factor as:

$$MSG = -20 \cdot \log (\max|F|) \quad (5)$$

MSG is going to be limited by the feedback gain factor (F), given by the acoustic characteristics of the room. F factor never is going to be 0, which means that the room does not exist.

Furthermore, the gain margin is defined as the difference between the MSG and the actual gain of the system. A gain margin of 2-3 dB is recommended to avoid audible artefacts [3].

2.3. Systems analysis

In this section, it will introduce the room where our electro-acoustic system is placed, as part of it. Is claimed in [2], that if the room and its electro-acoustic system satisfied the two conditions of *Nyquist Stability Criterion*, the system will oscillate at those particular frequencies for which the criterion is fulfilled. In this way, each particular set of room-microphone-loudspeakers will exhibit different sets of feedback frequencies.

If each component of the sound system reinforcement were reduced to its frequency response, it would be expected that feedback would appear in the frequency of the peaks. However, this is not a sufficient condition. But, if the phase shift also satisfies the criteria, then the system will oscillate. In the other hand, a dip in the response of a component of the system, cannot guarantee that feedback will not appear. The phase relations could be satisfied, and the overall gain is probably going to be greater than one.

Fig 5: Frequency response of a commercial microphone - Shure SM58

Experimental measurements in [2], yielded interesting results about how feedback behave in accordance with a component of the system frequency response. It can be observed that feedback frequencies do not correspond to the component frequency response peaks, but with steep slopes in the response. It is claimed that phase change rapidly as the response of a system does. So, in the neighbouring frequencies are satisfied the phase criteria. Of course, if at one peak the criterion is satisfied, feedback will appear. However, is more probable to find feedback frequencies at the slopes of the frequency response of any of the system. Finally, it would be expected that the flatter is the response of a system, the more reduced is the probability of having feedback on that range of frequencies.

Fig 6: Frequency response: Feedback vs. microphone

So, each component of the sound system contributes to feedback. It is obvious that microphones and loudspeakers would be more relevant than the amplifier. An amplifier tends to show a frequency response very flat, or, at least, with smooth variations. However, due to the technology of acoustical transducers (which will be not explained), microphones and loudspeaker tend to have a frequency response with peaks and dips, and as it was presented before, plays an important role in the feedback phenomenon.

Still there is another element in the overall system, the room, which is the most relevant one. This is because of the room itself, is the primary element contributing to the phase shift. But for practical purposes, the phase condition can be considered satisfied on a uniform basis with frequency [3].

2.4. Automatic feedback control

Automatic feedback control has been in the scope of research in the last years, so, this state of the art review is going to be focused in automatic methods, and these methods are classified into four classes:

- Phase-modulation
- Gain reduction
- Spatial filtering
- Room modeling

2.4.1. Phase-Modulation Methods

Frequency shifting (FS) of the microphone signals before these are amplified is one of the earliest approaches to acoustic feedback control. The optimal FS value is around 5 Hz, since the average frequency distance between two magnitude peaks is around 10 Hz [7]. A drawback of this approach is that the MSG increase is limited to 6 dB due to the audible beating effects caused by the shifting operation, and in other hand, the harmonic relations between tonal components are not preserved.

As was defined before, the two conditions of Nyquist criterion have to be satisfied to turn the system unstable, so, another approach is to avoid the phase condition by bypassing it employing a phase modulation. The Phase-modulating feedback control (PFC) approach has shown a good adaptation to transient's signals as the speech, but is not very suitable to audio signals that contain sustained tones. Finally, the perceptual evaluation of the sound quality using a PFC approach only has a single study [1].

2.4.2. Gain Reduction Methods

Another approach to acoustic feedback control is to prevent the magnitude condition of Nyquist criterion [5] by reducing the gain of the amplifier in the electroacoustic forward path. Depending on the width of the frequency band, three reduction methods can be discriminated:

- Automatic gain control (AGC): the gain is reduced equally in the entire frequency range.
- Automatic equalization (AEQ): the gain is reduced in critical sub-bands (in which the loop gain is close to unity).
- Notch-filter-based howling suppression (NHS): the gain is reduced in narrow frequency bands around critical frequencies.

Depending on the way these gain reduction methods are activated, two approaches can be distinguished:

1. Proactive detection: these methods are based on preventing howling effect by measuring spectral and time features of the feedback path online, that is, detecting a tendency to howling. Their aim is to eliminate howling before it occurs.
2. Reactive detection: these methods are based on eliminate howling after it happens. As well, is based on spectral and temporal features analysis of the microphone signal.

AGC methods do not increase the MSG since the gain of the entire system is reduced, but it is considered a “rescue procedure” [1], which is activated if all else fails. AEQ methods are limited by those sub-bands in which howling is detected. Finally, NHS methods can be classified into two categories, one-stage and two-stage. In one-stage methods the howling detection and notch filtering are performed at the same step, whereas in two-stage methods are performed separately. The most popular gain reduction method is the two-stage NHS

The main strength of gain reduction methods is their robustness, achieving an increase of the MSG up to around 10dB. However, not many experimental results of MSG increase values have been reported [1].

2.4.3. Spatial Filtering Methods

In this method, beam-forming filters processed the signals coming from an array of microphones, or, processed the signals going to an array of loudspeakers. This is made in order to modify the loop response GF. So, the aim of the design of these arrays is to place the main lobe of the microphone face to the source and having a null in the direction of the loudspeakers. In other hand, the design of an array of loudspeakers places the main lobe of the loudspeaker in the direction of the audience whereas it null in the direction of the microphone.

2.4.4. Room-Modelling Methods

These acoustic feedback control methods model the acoustic feedback path offline/online. Depending on how the model is applied two room-modelling methods can be distinguished:

- Adaptive Feedback Canceller (AFC): predict the feedback signal component in the microphone signal, and then, is eliminated from the microphone signal. The more accurate is the model of acoustic feedback path, the more elimination of acoustic coupling is achieved, yielding a nearly completely exclusion of acoustic feedback signal if the model is precise enough. Thus, a large increase of the MSG is obtained.
- Adaptive Inverse Filtering (AIF): this model works like the AFC, modelling the feedback path, but in this case the feedback signal is not removed from

the microphone, the feedback signal is injected in the closed signal loop in order to equalize the microphone signal.

The main drawback of room modelling methods lies in their computational complexity, but their main attractive is the fact that the feedback signal can be removed completely from the system. Because of this, newest research has been focused on these methods, and due to its complexity, new techniques, combining room modelling with others simplest approaches, has been proposed [1].

2.5. Current approaches for automatic feedback control

State of the art methods for acoustic feedback control have been showed in section 5, and in this one, current approaches for automatic acoustic feedback control are going to be presented: phase-modulating feedback control (phase modulation method), notch-filter-based howling suppression (gain reduction method) and adaptive feedback cancellation (room modeling method).

2.5.1. Phase-Modulating Feedback Control (PFC)

The aim of this method is to control the signal that arrives to the microphone modifying its phase in a way that every time that feedback signal arrives to the microphone, every frequency component has a different phase. This goal is achieved by inserting a phase modulation (PM) filter in the electroacoustic forward path.

The PM filter can be implemented in different ways, as sinusoidal PM, sinusoidal FM (frequency modulation) or FS (frequency shifting) filters, and this is the main strength of the PFC: only with a simple operation (modulation technique) and a

few parameter values (the more important are the modulation frequency and the modulation index) to decide, MSG can be improved. So, this approach is the simplest method to implement, conceptually and computationally.

In order to select the technique to implement the PM filter, the application of the feedback control plays an important role. The largest MSG increase is obtained by the FS, but, it is known that for music applications, this technique does not work really well because perceptually, it is a lossy technique. So, for music application it would be better to apply other techniques such as sinusoidal PM, but on the other hand, if the application is going to work in a speech sound reinforcement, the FS technique will be more appropriate.

Finally, the PFC has three main drawbacks:

- The achievable MSG is limited.
- The PM filter leads to signal distortion.
- The improvement of the MSG decreases as the number of channels increases in a multichannel system.

2.5.2. Notch-Filter-Based Howling Suppression (NHS)

The NHS method pretends to reduce the loop gain GF by reducing the neighbourhood of critical frequencies in a preventing way (proactive) or by suppressing howling after it occurs (reactive). The reactive approach is the most popular, besides, the two-stage method is more commonly used, which consists on activating the notch filters after howling is detected by the belonging algorithm. Two-stage means that first, a howling detection algorithm processes the signal from the microphone, and secondly, a bank of notch filters in the electroacoustic forward path is activated depending on the parameters extracted from the detection algorithm.

The most critical part of the NHS two-stage method is the howling detection algorithm. This algorithm consists on the detection of large magnitude sinusoidal

components (howling) in the microphone signal by frequency analysis. However, music and speech also have sinusoidal components in the frequency domain, so, the goal of a good howling detection algorithm is to discriminate between undesirable sinusoidal components in the microphone signal, keeping the music/speech quality. It can be observed in figure 7 (a) the loop gain of an unstable system in which a peak at 500 Hz has the larger magnitude. Moreover, in figure 7 (b) is very clear that howling occurs at a frequency of 500 Hz. This sinusoidal component does not have any harmonics components (as have voice or tonal music) and can be observed how the magnitude increases with time, an important temporal feature of howling component.

Fig 7: (a) Loop gain of an unstable closed-loop system and (b) spectrogram of the system [1]

The howling detection algorithm of a NHS two-stage method also has another function. The design of the notch filters are based on the features calculated by the algorithm, so, the appropriate parameters of the notch filters are decided by the howling detection algorithm. Typical parameters of design in notch filter banks are the center frequencies of each filter and their depth, depending on the howling magnitude values. Usually, 3dB bandwidth fixed to a value in a range of 1/10-1/60-octave notch filters are used [1].

The main advantage of this method is its robustness, since this approach is able to stabilize a system that has become unstable. Due to this reason, other algorithms such as PFC or AFC are supplemented with the NHS in order to stabilize the sound reinforcement once the main method has fail. Moreover, NHS' computational requirements are moderate, not as cheap as the PFC, but not as expensive as the AFC method, being the frequency analysis the main computational load of NHS.

The main inconvenient of the NHS approach is the large amount of parameters in the algorithm that have to be set: frame length, hop size, number of candidate howling components in each signal frame, discriminating features, thresholds for howling detection, number of variables for notch filters, and go on. Just a few guidelines are available for setting these algorithm parameters and a very few experimental results and no true comparisons between different NHS methods are available [1].

The NHS approach has the virtue to stabilize a sound reinforcement system without having to reduce the broadband gain, but, unfortunately, the MSG increase is not too much larger than the MSG increase with the PFC approach. Once the sinusoidal components of howling have been removed, the NHS approach delivers an increase of the MSG of 10 dB [1]. Besides, notch filtering yields distortion, which increases with the number of notch filters and the more the narrow is the bandwidth of notch filters. In terms of sound quality, this is an undesirable aspect.

2.5.3. Adaptive Feedback Cancellation (AFC)

The AFC approaches for acoustic feedback control consists on remove a predicted feedback signal from the microphone signal, in which there are a source signal and the feedback signal. This predicted feedback signal is calculated using a model of the acoustic feedback path by an adaptive filter that identifies the feedback path impulse response. Thus, the more similar the predicted feedback signal is to the actual feedback path, the more is the achievable increase of the

MSG. But, the complexity of this approach lies on its computational complexity due to the high order of the adaptive filter. For this reason, a completely elimination of feedback signal cannot be achieve. So, choosing an order of the adaptive filter large enough to obtain a satisfying MSG increase would be the best compromise between computational complexity and acoustic feedback control performance.

The AFC approach needs an initialization, known as regularization. Regularization is a technique, which takes room acoustic information, from the acoustic feedback path impulse response, and incorporates it to the adaptive filtering algorithm.

The AFC method is considered to be the most promising solution to acoustic feedback control [1] due to the fact that feedback effect can be completely eliminated, and in consequence, a large increase of MSG can be achieved (15-20 dB [1]). AFC approach preserves sound quality, however, with some techniques, distortion seems to be unavoidable.

Like was introduced before, the main drawback of AFC approach is its computational complexity, even with a cheap adaptive filter algorithm. Nevertheless, several real-time AFC implementations have been reported [1]. Due to this complexity, also multichannel applications are limited, in which the complexity of the adaptive filter would increase by the factor of multiplying the number of microphones by the number of loudspeakers.

3. METHODOLOGY

In this section, the methodology for the measurement of the Maximum Stable Gain (MSG) is presented. The methodology fuses the analysis of the system microphone-loudspeaker-room, with state of the art tools for audio analysis.

The methodology defines a quantitative threshold of the feedback onset from in situ measurements and defines the influence of the systems. To achieve this goal, a controlled scenario for acoustic feedback simulation has been built, where measurements and recordings have been taken place.

A second goal of this methodology is a classification approach between feedback and non-feedback prone scenarios using machine-learning techniques. An audio dataset have been built based on measurements and recordings in order to train the system. Spectral descriptor analysis has been realized to determine machine-learning techniques and parameters.

3.1. Controlled scenario for acoustic feedback simulation

The first step is to generate feedback in a controlled scenario. Due to the high sound pressure the system can be achieved, is necessary to control the system in order to do not be damage. For this reason, every element of the sound system is well placed, and gain control is carefully manipulated.

In order to simulate an ordinary feedback scenario, microphones and loudspeakers have been placed as they could be for a practical situation. So, loudspeaker S (see figure 8) that is the source, is aiming the audience, which is

placed where the reference microphone is. In the same way, the loudspeaker Ls (amplification system) is aiming the public.

Fig 8: Acoustic feedback simulation set-up

Several systems have been placed in this scenario:

- Source (S): is the origin of the sound, as could be a speaker or a music program. This loudspeaker is auto-amplified.
- Measure microphone: this element is one of the protagonists of feedback. Is placed just in front of the source (10 cm) and on axis. This microphone will be change in order to compare different system, but for the first simulation, it has been a famous voice microphone: Shure sm58.
- Gain control: since the loudspeakers are auto-amplified (different models, different amplifiers) gain control have been routed to a computer with a DAW (Digital Audio Workstation) in order to do not manipulate several

amplifiers. So, the gain of the loudspeakers is fixed to a level in which feedback is achieved, and reduced by the computer for its control.

- Mixing console: responsible of routing. Every single element of the entire system (except for the measurement system) goes through it.
- Loudspeaker (Ls): is the element is going to be force to howl. This auto-amplified loudspeaker is aiming to the audience, and its role would be to amplify the sound that comes from the source.
- Reference Microphone: this element measures the level from Ls and would be able to capture the MSG measurement.
- Audio Interface: is connected to the computer with the measurement software, necessary to control the gain of the microphones and power the reference one (phantom power). Is responsible of converting the acoustic signals to digital signals.
- Measurement software: application that compares both microphones in order to measure the MSG.

All this elements work together to create a feedback scenario. Furthermore, both microphones signals (measure and reference) goes to computer that, thanks to the software (SmaartV7 [11]), measures sound pressure levels. The entire system works in this way:

1. The measure microphone (velocity) is placed in front of the source loudspeakers, at 10cm, on-axis. Is placed in this way to emulate a speaker talking to a microphone. As is demonstrated in [6], proximity effect of the microphone would not take part into the feedback loop, since reflections will not experience the low frequency gain. Furthermore, largest sensitivity takes place on-axis, so is oriented in this way to achieve feedback as soon as possible.

Fig 9: Measure microphone location

2. In the other hand, the reference microphone is placed in front of the monitor loudspeaker, at 1m and on-axis. This distance is a standard for acoustic measurements. And as was justified in the paragraph before, on-axis, the microphone has its maximum sensitivity. This microphone ends in the audio interface connected to the measure computer.

Fig 10: Microphone-loudspeaker setup

3. Then, the DAW generates pink noise. This signal is used in order to excite all the frequencies in such a way that, the energy of each octave band is the same, as a music programme could be.

Fig 11: Pink noise - signal used in the experiment

4. Once the signal is goes through the source loudspeaker, the measure microphone catches the pink noise. The microphone signal goes then to an audio splitter, which divides the signal into two. One of then goes to the mixing desk to be re-driven to the monitor loudspeaker, and the other one ends into the audio interface of the measure computer.
5. The next step is to adjust the gain of both microphones until is the same one.
6. Following, the gain of the monitor loudspeaker is increased gradually until howling is achieved.
7. At the same time as 6, the reference microphone catches the signal that goes through the monitor loudspeaker.
8. Finally, a real-time comparison takes place in the measurement computer, which runs Smaart V7.

Adopting this set up, several measurements have been done as are described on the next section.

3.2. Measurements and recordings of feedback simulation

For each test, it has been taken an audio recording. This audio recording would help later to make an exhaustive analysis of the data collected. However, in the first approach, SPL data has been annotated. As one of the goals is to determinate the MSG, gain has been also wrote down.

Nevertheless, the experimental set up has been tested before. Few trials have been proven in order to achieve the optimal methodology. These tests have been done with the same equipment and source-microphone-loudspeaker location, in order to compare each test. A cardioid microphone has been used to take first notes. However, later, this polar pattern is compared with the super-cardioid. Both are typical patterns used for catch a speaker's voice.

3.2.1. Commercial microphones tests

In these tests, several commercial microphones have been tried. Manufactures provide the datasheet, so, frequency response can be extracted from it to make an exhaustive comparison with feedback response.

The same procedure as showed in section 3.1 has been done. Thus, 2 important characteristics have been extracted: the feedback frequency and the MSG of each microphone. Table 1 shows these 2 parameters.

Table 1: Feedback frequency and MSG of tested microphones

	Shure sm58	Shure sm57	Sennheiser e845	Shure Beta 58A
Feedback freq. (Hz)	6.200	7.200	4.500	7.900
MSG (dB)	9	12	8	6

Under these test, it seems like feedback appears at that frequencies in which both, microphones and loudspeaker, have their maximum variability in magnitude. Also, their maximum magnitude value it is in that range. In section 4 will be an exhaustive analysis of this data. However, in order to build a suitable audio datasheet, observing that feedback can be heard in this range is enough. So, it can be claimed that, for this particular set of microphones and loudspeaker, feedback would be appear between 4,5kHz and 7,9kHz. Nevertheless, a range from 4kHz to 8kHz has been used in order to have a margin.

Fig 12: Shure sm57 frequency response

Fig 13: Genelec 1029A frequency response

In table 1 can also be observed that, in this case, cardioid microphones (sm58 and sm57) can achieve a higher MSG than super-cardioid microphones (e845 and beta 58A). This occurs because of the room and location of systems. It is fundamental to indicate that the room used for the recordings was a music studio, which is very absorbent in the speaker area. However, the audience location has diffusers on the

walls. This means that mostly of the energy would come back to the microphone by its back, and, super-cardioid microphones have a lobe there. So, it could be predicted that, changing the location of loudspeaker-microphone, MSG could change as well for both polar patterns. Thus, can be claimed that, in a given feedback scenario, it would be a specific polar pattern that can better reject feedback.

3.3. Audio dataset

According to the experiments realised, the audio dataset has been built. The library contains a wide number of samples with sounds of different nature, such as violins, guitars, speech, full bands (of different genders), etc. Audio samples have been extracted from *freesound.org* [12], a collaborative database of sounds. Thus, 2 different datasets have been used; one with the original audio samples, and the other one with the same files with added feedback frequency. Feedback frequency has been generated randomly according to the experimental approach explained in section 3.2.2. So, in order to simulate the same feedback scenario that have been tried, feedback frequencies stays in a limited range, from 4kHz to 8kHz.

Fig 14: Spectrogram of an audio sample with feedback

3.4. Spectral descriptors analysis and machine learning

The last step of the methodology proposed, is the spectral analysis of the audio dataset. The analysis is based on spectral descriptors [8].

3.4.1. Feature extraction

The descriptors extracted are the ones related with the spectral information. It was observed in the previous tests that these are the features that better describe the acoustic feedback phenomenon, since is closely related with the spectrum. So, a “.csv” file has been generated from the audio dataset, in which there are 2 classes: feedback (“yes”) and no feedback (“no”). Table 2 shows the structure of the file with the descriptors.

Table 2: CSV file example, 3 first tracks (“no” feedback)

sCentroid	sCrest	sFlatness	sFlux	sKurtosis	sRolloff	sSkewness	sSpread	ZCR	class
3024.9	40.827	0.20634	0.035466	7.2858	3500	1.9527	3778.2	2633.1	no
3061.1	57.755	0.15436	0.024249	13.285	3451.9	2.546	3387.2	3665.2	no
3112.5	50.683	0.24136	0.026455	9.4606	3004.2	2.1989	3888.6	2584.1	no

3.4.2. Automatic classification

Finally, in order to classify the sounds into feedback vs. non-feedback the CSV file has been analysed with *Weka* [13].

The first approach has been to visualize which features are more selective. In figure 19 can be observed Spectral Roll-off vs. ZCR. Both descriptors are good since the class of the sounds is separate in both axes.

Fig 15: Fig 16: Roll-off vs. ZCR

Combinations of Spectral Centroid, Spectral Kurtosis and Spectral Skewness yield similar plots, but in figures in which Spectral Roll-off and ZCR is compared, this separation in both axes become more evident. So, the start point for doing the analysis has been the Spectral Roll-off feature vs. ZCR feature.

An example of bad descriptors is show in figure 21. In this case, is impossible to distinguish the class of the sounds. It shows a random distribution.

Fig 17: an example of bad descriptors

4. RESULTS

In this section are presented results from an exhaustive analysis of recordings. First, in order to define a threshold of the feedback onset, a maximum stable gain curve has been defined. Then, the influence of the systems involved in the acoustic feedback phenomenon is presented, paying special attention to on the feedback frequency of several microphones available on the current market. To conclude, classification approach results show up.

4.1. Description of the maximum stable gain curve

As it was defined in section 2.2, the maximum stable gain is the maximum amplification that a feedback system can achieve before it becomes unstable, in other words, it starts howling. So, in order to represent the maximum stable gain, sound pressure level (SPL) and gain are drawn in the same graphic.

Fig 18: maximum stable gain curve (SPL vs. Gain)

The curve represents that, as the amplification gain of the system increases (forward path), the SPL in the audience does. At the early increase of the gain, the SPL grows in a linear way, since feedback component is barely relevant. But, as soon as gain reaches a certain level, artefacts start to appear and the slope of the curve changes. This change means that SPL increase is no longer linear, and the slope becomes steeper. In this stage, feedback component is noticeable. The last section of the curve represents feedback. Here, the slope of the curve changes drastically, exceeding over 10dBs of SPL per each dB of increase in the amplification gain. The system starts to howl. For more information about these three sections of feedback (linear-artefacts-howling), refer to [2][6].

The curve is defined as follows:

$$aSPL - bG - c = 0 \Rightarrow aSPL = bG + c$$

In which SPL is the sound pressure level in the audience, G is the amplification gain of the system and 'a', 'b' and 'c' are constants. Constant 'a', corresponds to the calibration of the microphone, which should be 1 in order to compare both microphones (testing and audience one). The slope of the curve is given by 'b', meanwhile 'c', is just the background noise, which can be considered 0 as soon as the SPL is around 10dB over it.

So, the curve is re-written as:

$$SPL = bG$$

In the linear section, the slope changes in a small range. When this value of the slope gets over a certain threshold, can be affirmed that the system is about to become unstable. Moreover, when this threshold is exceeded, artefacts can be heard.

It has been observed, after several tests with different models of microphones, that the threshold, which separates the linear section of the curve and the one where artefacts appear, is 1,5. So:

$$1 < b < 1,5 \rightarrow \text{linear section (usual behaviour)}$$

$$1,5 \leq b \rightarrow \text{artifacts (just below feedback)}$$

Finally, in the feedback section, the slope tends to infinite, however is limited by physical characteristics of the system. The threshold that divides artefacts section and feedback one depends on the manufacturing of the microphone. This slope is going to be extremely related to the feedback frequency. In the next section, a detailed analysis of this frequency is shown.

Fig 19: MSG curves of different microphone models

4.2. Feedback frequency

Manufacturers provide a datasheet of each of their product. This information has been used to compare different frequency responses of several electro-acoustic systems.

Figure 20 shows different frequency responses (gain vs. frequency) of the microphones tested (colours) and the speaker used (black). Frequency responses have been fenced between 4kHz and 8kHz, which is the range where all feedback frequencies appear. As is claimed in section 2.3, feedback frequencies will appear in those regions where can be found changes in the frequency response. And due to the manufacturing process of microphones and loudspeakers, these oscillations on their frequency responses tends to be in this range.

Has been observed that is hard to predict the exact feedback frequency since in this range, phase changes rapidly. In other words, small changes in the environment (microphone-loudspeaker position, materials, etc.) can modify the feedback path, and change the frequency that satisfies the phase condition of Nyquist criterion.

Moreover, have been observed that, either positive or negative slopes can generate oscillations in the system. Comparing both, microphone and loudspeaker frequency responses, one by one, different situations can be observed. For example, feedback frequency of a Shure sm58 is 6,2 kHz, that corresponds to a peak in the loudspeaker response and a decreasing slope of the microphone response. However, for a Shure sm57, feedback frequency corresponds to a dip in the microphone response. Check table 3 and figure 20 for more examples.

Table 3: feedback frequencies of different microphones

	Shure sm58	Shure sm57	Sennheiser e845	Shure Beta 58A
Feedback freq. (kHz)	6.2	7.2	4.5	7.9

In conclusion, feedback frequency can be predicted in a limited range. This range corresponds to the superposition of frequency responses, microphone and loudspeaker. The area where can be found more oscillations (peaks and dips), would has more probability to contain the feedback frequency.

4.3. Classification approach

After trying some classifiers (such as: k -nearest neighbours algorithm, with different number of neighbours; SMO, support vector machine; or Naive Bayes classifiers) good results have been obtained with *Decision Trees*. This algorithm is easy to understand, and can yield the threshold that could be use to distinguish between feedback and non-feedback sounds. In particular, the J48 classifier have been the best one observed, since it has the highest ratio of correctly classified instances. Moreover, incorrectly classified instances are equally distributed among false positives and false negatives, so there is no bias to any of the classes. It can be observed the decision tree in figure 20. Finally, using a training set, the correctly classified instances percentage rises, whereas incorrectly classified instances

decrease keeping their equal distribution. Figure 21 shows the summary of the results.

Fig 20: tree (J48) for Spectral Roll-off vs. ZCR

```

=== Run information ===

Scheme:weka.classifiers.trees.J48 -C 0.25 -M 2
Relation:      csvLab5-weka.filters.unsupervised.attribute.Remove-R1-5,7-8
Instances:    90
Attributes:   3
              sRolloff
              ZCR
              class
Test mode:evaluate on training data

=== Classifier model (full training set) ===

J48 pruned tree
-----

sRolloff <= 3586.5
|  ZCR <= 1576.1: no (20.0)
|  ZCR > 1576.1
|  |  sRolloff <= 2988.8
|  |  |  ZCR <= 2188.9
|  |  |  |  sRolloff <= 1485: si (4.0/1.0)
|  |  |  |  sRolloff > 1485: no (8.0)
|  |  |  |  ZCR > 2188.9: si (6.0)
|  |  |  |  sRolloff > 2988.8: no (11.0)
|  |  |  |  sRolloff > 3586.5: si (41.0/5.0)
sRolloff > 3586.5: si (41.0/5.0)

Number of Leaves   :    6
Size of the tree   :   11

Time taken to build model: 0.02 seconds

=== Evaluation on training set ===
=== Summary ===
Correctly Classified Instances      84           93.3333 %
Incorrectly Classified Instances     6            6.6667 %
Kappa statistic                     0.8667
Mean absolute error                  0.1142
Root mean squared error              0.239
Relative absolute error              22.8455 %
Root relative squared error          47.797 %
Total Number of Instances           90

=== Detailed Accuracy By Class ===

          TP Rate  FP Rate  Precision  Recall  F-Measure  ROC Area  Class
          0.867    0        1          0.867   0.929     0.947    no
          1        0.133   0.882     1        0.938     0.947    si
Weighted Avg.  0.933    0.067   0.941     0.933   0.933     0.947

=== Confusion Matrix ===
 a  b  <-- classified as
39  6  |  a = no
 0 45  |  b = si

```

Fig 21: summary of the classifier model

5. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE RESEARCH

5.1. Conclusion

A new methodology to measure the maximum stable gain in an acoustic feedback scenario has been introduced. It brings to technicians a method to optimize rooms, which contains an amplification system. Howling is unavoidable, but if the limitations of the sound system are known, a good selection of each component in the chain could increase the maximum stable gain. Therefore, a robust and a reliable system could be installed.

Furthermore, the maximum stable gain curve has been defined. It has been established into 3 sections, in terms of its slope. In other hand, has been quantifying a threshold to determine the section just below feedback.

Finally, a threshold of a spectral descriptor for automatic classification has been defined. After trying the dataset with several algorithms, a good option to classify sounds with feedback and without feedback has been observed to be the *Decision Trees* algorithm. To improve results, the J48 classifier with a training set have been computed, yielding 93.33% of correctly classified instances (before: 82.22%; with 10-fold cross validation to avoid over-fitting) and a confusion matrix equilibrated with no bias to any of the classes. Then, the threshold extracted from this process is: 3586.5. This threshold could help to characterize the behaviour of the acoustic feedback.

5.2. Future research

The methodology exposed considers gain of the forward path to make comparisons with the SPL in the audience and is used to define the maximum stable gain curve. It would be interesting to re-built tests by using the feedback gain as reference. It could contribute to find the point in which feedback starts to be noticeable, not as negative behaviour of the sound system (artefacts or howling) but as an added sound reinforcement.

An objective definition of the maximum stable gain has been defined. Since the threshold given could vary depending on the characteristics of the room, a subjective measure of the noticeable artefacts could help to improve it, even to set up a subjective error of the measure. For example, a given scenario yields that when the slope of the maximum stable gain curve is more than 1,6, then, the sound system is about to start howling (artefacts are audible). But for a listener in a specific position, these artefacts can be heard before that slope is achieved. In the other hand, another listener could not hear them (could be close to absorbers that eliminate that component). So, an error of the threshold could be defined.

Finally, the threshold of the spectral descriptor to detect feedback could be adjusted in order to detect when the artefacts start to appear.

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